

Effect of Workforce Diversity on Employee Performance in Kenyan Public Sector: A Case of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology

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Abstract:- Workforce diversity is a contemporary reality that organizations cannot overlook. It is important for institutions to develop policies and structures to ensure that reflect a diverse workforce to enhance employee performance. This study sought to determine whether workforce diversity has a significant effect on employee performance in Kenyan public sector. The research focused on the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology as a case study and was based on the main objective which was to determine the effect of workforce diversity on employee performance. Gender Schema and Intersectionality theories guided the research study to contextualize the aspect of workforce diversity, specifically gender diversity, and its effect on employee performance. The study used descriptive research design. Fischer's formula at 95% confidence level gave a sample size of 128 respondents out of 860 target population. Questionnaires were used to collect data. Data analysis was done through descriptive statistics of mean, frequency, standard deviation, correlation, and regression analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Cronbach's alpha reliability test was 0.752 and 0.781 for employee performance and gender diversity respectively. Findings showed that gender diversity has a significant positive correlation to employee performance ($\beta_1 = 0.163$, $p < 0.05$). Also, Pearson's correlation shows that workforce diversity positively impacts on employee performance by 78% ($r = .785^{**}$, $P = .000$) at 5% level of significance. R-square value of 0.783 also shows gender diversity impacts employee performance by over 78%. The study concludes that workforce diversity in terms of gender has a positive significant effect on employee performance. It thus recommends more research to be done in other public sectors, private sectors, and on other diversity variables.

Keywords:- Workforce Diversity, Gender Diversity, Employee Performance, Public Sector.

I. INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is a relatively contentious topic of discussion among professionals and scholars in the Human Resources field. Researchers and experts have come up with various explanations to define employee performance. However, most scholars agree on the fact that employee performance is paramount to organizational output and service delivery. According to Armstrong (2021), employee performance refers to the extent to which an

organization's staff accomplishes duties, tasks, roles and behavior in the workplace. On the other hand, Alromaihi et.al. (2017) define employee performance as a set of workplace behavior aimed at accomplishing results. Employee performance thus acts as the determinant of how well or poorly one is doing in relation to specific tasks.

Since the industrialization era, business owners as well as stakeholders have emphasized performance. Employees remain the most valuable assets in any organization hence exemplary discharge of their respective duties directly affects overall institution's performance and competitive advantage. Research outlines specific variables used to measure workforce performance. Quantity and quality of product or service delivery is a vital indicator of performance (Armstrong & Taylor, 2023). Decision making skills, creativity and innovation also reflect employee performance.

Workforce diversity on the other hand refers to differences among individual employees in an organization based on characteristics like gender, age, culture, and physical ability or inability (Kundu & Mor, 2017). Armstrong & Taylor (2023), state that diversity involves valuing all employees despite their physical, intellectual, and cultural differences. Workplace diversity considers the visible and invisible differences like race, gender, age, disability, and personalities. The management team can harness diversity to realize a highly productive work environment for competitive advantage. Globalization and technological advancement have catalyzed the fast nature of changing work environment. Diversity's inclusive concept thus remains a pressing issue among business stakeholders to remain relevant in the market.

From the international perspective, scholars continue to emphasize the importance of having a diverse workforce and its relation to employee performance. In his work, Kharroubi (2021), notes that diversity no longer implies heterogeneity of the workforce in a country, but rather its composition. Data from the U.S Bureau of Labor Statistics (2023) shows that as of 2019, foreign born persons made up 17.0 % of the labor force. Likewise, in 2020 people living with disability comprised 17.9% of total labor force.

In Africa, many scholars and Human resource professionals continue to explore various dimensions of workforce diversity and its effect on employee performance in organizations. Mousa (2021) did research on effect of gender diversity on workplace happiness among academics

in Egypt. Using questionnaires and t-test methods, the research concluded that female academics perceive diversity practices better than males. Setati et.al (2019) carried out a study to determine how ethnic and gender diversity affects performance among employees in South African higher learning institutions. Research findings showed that diversities in gender and ethnicity have a directly proportional influence on employee performance. However, sexual harassment, prejudice and discrimination dominate most African organizations.

In Kenya, Anyango and Florah (2019) carried out a research study on relationship between workforce diversity and performance among employees of Kisumu Law Courts. Using variables like age, gender, education attainment, and religion, the study found out that workplace diversity has direct influence on overall employee and organizational performance. Another study done by Odhiambo, Gachoka, and Rambo (2018) explored the effect of age diversity on performance of employees in universities in Western Kenya. Despite the positive relation between diversity and performance, the research noted discrepancies in implementation of diversity in Kenyan universities.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Employee performance in the public sector remains an issue of concern among investors and the government. The Vision 2030 economic pillar projected an increase of the GDP by 10% from all sectors. However, according to Ogola (2017), the Kenya Institute of Public Policy and Research and Analysis (KIPPRA) indicate that the public sector in Kenya has been experiencing negative growth for the last five years compared to the private sector since more is spent on wages and less is received in form of revenue. A report done by the Kenya Private Sector Alliance to the World Bank on private sector development shows that the sector contributes to more than 70% while public sector contributes 30% of the nation's gross domestic product (GDP) as of 2020. KIPPRA's 2020 economic report spells that only seven out of the forty-seven counties (15%) were able to meet the one billion annual revenue mark in 2019. Performance in the public sector remains dismal due to poor human management policies like diversity and performance management (Odhiambo, Gachoka, and Rambo, 2018). For instance, an analysis of the parliament of Kenya membership shows that population of elected women representatives in the twelfth parliament stagnates at 16% which is below the 33% stipulated by the constitution of Kenya (The Parliament of Kenya, 2023). The margin in gender representation reflects that the public sector employee performance has a direct relationship with diversity in the workplace.

A workforce with employees of various age groups, gender, and cultural background tends to make better decisions on critical issues. Highly diversified employees deliver quality services and products, and are more creative (Mekasha, 2020). Despite low employee performance index in the Kenyan public sector, the ministry of education is making efforts towards inclusivity by having a diverse workforce through several programs like compliance to

affirmative action during recruitment and appointment exercise. The Ministry of Education aims at having at least a third of its population comprise of women, youth, and individuals from marginalized regions. However, the institution and the public sector in general is yet to achieve the expected threshold of gender diversity representation in its employee population not merely as a compliance exercise but as an integrated performance policy (Chepkemoi, Rop, & Chepkwony, 2022). Though previous studies have been done in relation to workforce diversity and employee performance, most scholars focus on the variables but not directly linking it to employee performance. Also, to a great extent, evidence-based suggestions on how organizations can maximize benefits from workforce diversity are scarce. Other than profitability which results from productivity, other indicators like decision making, meeting set targets, and creativity cannot be measured in absolute terms. For instance, Mousa (2021) notes that female academics positively perceive diversity and its effect on employee performance more than their male counterparts but that cannot be quantified. This study, hence, intended to determine the effects of employee diversity on employee performance in the Ministry of Education headquarters.

A. Research Questions of the Study

- To what extent does workforce diversity affect employee performance at the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology?
- To what extent does gender diversity affect employee performance at the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology?

B. Objectives of the Research Study

➤ General Objective

- To determine effect of workforce diversity on employee performance at the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology.

➤ Specific objectives

- To examine the effect of gender diversity on employee performance at the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology.

➤ Hypothesis of the Research Study

- Workforce diversity does not affect employee performance at the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology.
- Gender diversity does not affect employee performance at the Ministry of Education Science, and Technology.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Defining Concepts

- **Workforce Diversity**-Differences among individual employees in an organization based on characteristics like gender, age, education, culture, and physical ability or inability (Kundu & Mor, 2017). Armstrong further adds that it is the composition of employees in terms of personal attributes and physical features (2021). Though most of these features remain constant, some have evolved for instance gender is transforming from the

traditional binary concept of male and female to include the LGBTQ community.

- **Gender Diversity-** Though contentiously debated, gender diversity traditionally refers to the measure of ratio of hire, promotion, and payment of employees of males to females in the workplace (Mousa, 2021). However, Marinova, Plantenga and Remery (2016) argue that gender goes way over and above the traditional male and female descriptions to include the transgender community in the contemporary society. The research focused on three variables which include male to female employees’ ratio, fair treatment, and equity policies within the organization.
- **Employee Performance-**Armstrong (2021) defines employee performance as how an employee completes tasks, fulfils designated roles and duties, and generally behaves in the organization. Each organization uses different tools to review and measure performance rates of its employees depending on the company’s goals and objectives. The researcher majored in meeting set

targets, decision making and problem-solving ability, creativity, and innovation as employee performance indicators.

- **Public sector-**Refers to the entire spectrum of the economy with organizations and institutions that offer basic goods and services to the public under the financing and guidance of the government in line with established constitutional mandates (Odhiambo, Gachoka, and Rambo, 2018). These include military, public education, health care, transport, and housing among others operated through government ministries, commissions, and parastatals.

IV. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The independent variable in workforce diversity was gender while employee performance is the dependent variable. Each variable was measured using three indicators and can be presented as shown in the framework below

Fig. 1: Variables
Source: Researcher (2023)

B. Theoretical Framework

➤ *Intersectionality Theory (Kimberley Crenshaw, 1989)*

Crenshaw, a writer on civil rights was the first to coin the intersectionality theory in feminism. Though contextualized in America, and paying more attention to African American women, Crenshaw’s idea is to emphasize on the place of both genders in formal employment setting. Traditionally, the place of males goes unopposed while females remain with limited opportunities within the workplace. Crenshaw argues that women should be equally given an opportunity to showcase their abilities and creativity in jobs whose merit standards they meet. The author argues that managers and leaders should follow due processes in recruitment, promotion, and dismissal for each employee irrespective of gender.

Mithaug (1996) further improved the theory by introducing ‘Equal Opportunity’ theory which advocates for fair societal prospects and determination for all people. In relation to advancements done after woman suffrage period, Mithaug notes that people should be given equal chances to deliver irrespective of their color, race, or gender. Mithaug and Crenshaw agree on the perspective of everyone and equal opportunity at the workplace and the society while Crenshaw centers on the female gender. Gender diversity and employee performance is still a work in progress for most organizations across the globe. A consideration of the intersectionality theory in the workplace recognizes that different genders have varying strengths and weaknesses which if put together can produce synergy in performance and overall output by employees.

➤ *Gender Schema Theory (Sandra L. Bem, 1981)*

This is a cognitive philosophy which addresses how children process and represent gender-related information. According to Bem, children form an inclination towards gender from a very early stage. As children grow, they identify themselves as boys or girls and as such, begin to selectively remember, pay attention to, and act on gender-related information like dressing and colors. These influence their inferences and judgement into adulthood. For instance, a five-year old girl aspires to become a nurse while a boy aspires to be a pilot, but this improves with time. Schema theory fit well into gender diversity among employees. For example, employees’ understanding of work processes, policies, and work conditions are shaped by their gender perceptions which in turn affect their performance. Cherry criticizes the theory and notes that it fails to consider the role played by biology or social interactions on gender development (2018). Also, one cannot measure gender schemas before understanding their contents since it accounts for the process rather than the content.

C. Empirical Literature Review

➤ *Effect of Gender Diversity on Employee Performance*

Krishnan (2020) did a research study on workplace gender diversity and its effect on employee performance. The case study was a food processing industry in Kerala, India. The study adopted descriptive research method. Questionnaires were administered to a sample size of 230 respondents. Data analysis was done through ANOVA, regression, and correlation analysis. Findings showed that gender diversity makes a vital contribution to employee

performance through high employee engagement, productivity, and satisfaction.

Mousa (2021) carried out research on Egyptian public universities to find out the effect of gender diversity on workforce happiness. The researcher administered questionnaires on a sample size of 960 academics from three public universities but received response from 320 respondents. Cronbach’s alpha analysis gave a figure of 0.8 showing that gender diversity has a positive relationship with employee happiness. However, Mousa (2021) notes that workplace happiness is pegged on other factors such as job description and management policies thus gender diversity is not a sufficient tool to measure happiness. Notably, only gender was studied as a workforce diversity to affect employee performance yet there exist other diversity measures.

Chepkmoi, Rop and Chepkwony (2022) carried out a research study on relationship between gender diversity on employee performance in the county government of Bomet. Out of the 3,320-target population, the researchers used fisher’s formula to get a sample size of 91 employees. The data collection instrument used was structured questionnaire. Using Cronbach’s coefficient formula, the research obtained an alpha coefficient of 0.850. The research employed regression and correlation analysis to analyze the data. Results established that gender diversity has a significant influence on employee performance by 72.3%. The study only centered on gender diversity to determine employee performance.

➤ *Effect of Workforce Diversity on Employee Performance*

Khan, Sohail, Sufyan, Uddin, and Basit (2019) conducted a research study on effect of workforce diversity on employee performance in institutions of higher learning in Swabi district, Pakistan. Data was collected from a random sample of 440 faculty members using questionnaires. Amir and his colleagues used various statistical techniques through the SPSS software to analyze data. Diversity variables measured included gender, age, and

education. Results showed a significant relationship between workforce diversity and employee performance in terms of problem-solving skills, creativity, and critical thinking.

Mekasha (2020) undertook a research study on the effect of workforce diversity on employee performance. This was a case study of Save the Children, Ethiopia. The research targeted 144 employees. Semi-structured interviews and a five-point Likert scale questionnaire were used to collect data. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics method through SPSS version 26.0. Results showed that workforce diversity has a significant effect on employee performance as it maintains a competitive edge and encourages creativity.

Barang’a and Maende (2019) did a research study on effect workforce diversity on employee performance in the Attorney General’s Office in Kenya. From a sample size of 55 employees, data was collected using questionnaires. Data analysis was done using regression analysis. From the findings, the organization had a performance rate of 78%. The independent variables measured were age, educational background, ethnicity, and age which all gave positive correlations above 0.5. Employee performance variables measured were work quality, creativity or innovation, and achievement of targets.

V. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design by surveying standardized questionnaire which systematically measures a population through various research methods to measure and analyze variables under study(Pandey & Pandey, 2021). Descriptive survey research design has an advantage over other designs since it measures phenomena the way they are, answering what, where, how, and when questions (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2019).The population constituted 860 employees across various departments at the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology as shown in the table 1.

Table 1: Target Population

Department	Number of Employees	Percentage
Finance	15	1.7%
Human Resource	208	24.2%
ICT	152	17.7%
Quality Assurance	90	10.5%
Vocational and Technical Training	98	11.4%
Early Learning & Basic Education	45	5.2%
University Education & Research	52	6%
Post Training & Skills Development	60	7%
Subordinate Staff	140	16.3%
Total	860	100%

Source: HR Directorate, Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (2023)

B. Sample and sampling technique

The research study adopted stratified random sampling technique which divides the sample into strata or sections. Stratified random sampling has an advantage of increasing statistical efficiency by creating a clear representation of the population under study (Sama et.al., 2020). It also allows

use of different data analysis methods. The sample size represented each department in equal proportions to the total population. The researcher used Fischer’s formula to determine the sample size. The formula is as shown below.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 p (1-p)}{d^2} = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.5) (1-0.5)}{(0.08)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

Z = standard normal deviation value for the level of confidence. For instance, 95% level of confidence is 1.96.

d= margin of error or level of precision at 0.08 for CI at 92%

p= proportion to be estimated at 0.5

Therefore, the sample size is calculated as follows:

$$n = 150$$

Since the population is less than 10,000, the sample size will further be adjusted as follows:

$$N_o = n / (1 + ((n-1)/N))$$

$$N_o = 150 / (1 + ((150-1)/860))$$

$$N_o = 128$$

Table 2: Sample Distribution

Department	Population	Sample	Percentage
Finance	15	2	1.7%
Human Resources	208	31	24.2%
ICT	152	22	17.7%
Quality Assurance	90	13	10.5%
Vocational & Technical Training	98	15	11.4%
Early Learning & Basic Education	45	7	5.2%
University Education & Research	52	8	6%
Post Training & Skills Development	60	9	7%
Subordinate Staff	140	21	16.3%
Total	860	128	100%

Source: HR Directorate, Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (2023)

The research study used primary data to obtain first-hand information about workforce diversity and its effect on employee performance. The researcher used a closed-ended questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. In this study, the questionnaire had a Likert scale with statements of five options ranging from ‘strongly disagree’ to ‘strongly agree’. After obtaining authorization from relevant authorities, questionnaires were distributed for data collection.

C. Validity and Reliability of Research Instruments

The research used face validity which according to Pandey & Pandey (2021) shows a significant ratio of factors which subjectively judge the relevance of the data collection instrument to give satisfactory measure of the phenomenon. The researcher used Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient to determine reliability of the research instruments. Results obtained showed the research instrument was reliable as it contained items relevant to the study as indicated by the Content Validity Index for all the variables which was above the acceptable threshold of internal consistency of 0.7 On average (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2019)

Table 3: Reliability Analysis

Variable	No. of Items	≥ 0.7	Comment
Employee Performance	6	0.752	Reliable
Gender Diversity	6	0.781	Reliable

Source: Researcher Data (2023)

Data analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25. Inferential analysis of coefficients, correlation, and regression analysis, incorporating ANOVA and R-square, was also used to find out if there exists a cause-effect relationship between workforce diversity and employee performance. The analyzed data was presented using frequency distribution tables and percentages.

The formula of regression analysis is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$$

Where:

Y is the dependent variable, employee performance

The β are the coefficients, and

The α is a constant

X is a set of independent variables of workforce diversity indicators measured against the dependent variable of employee performance

Whereby,

X₁ is gender and

The ε is the error of estimation

VI. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This was assessed using a 5- point Likert scale where strongly agree = 5 represented the highest scale and strongly disagree = 1 represented the lowest point. Analysis was done using mean and standard deviation. Mean closer to 1 meant there was a disagreement while mean closer to 2.5

meant neutrality and mean closer to 5 signified a strong agreement. The objective was to examine the effect of gender diversity on employee performance at the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology. This was assessed and the results given below.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on Gender Diversity.

Statement	%	%	%	%	%	Mean	Std. Dev.
Male to female ratio at the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology meets the constitutional affirmative rule	9.0%	15.0%	20.0%	38.0%	18.0%	3.4	1.2
There are more female than male employees at the senior managerial level in the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology.	15.0%	20.0%	24.0%	24.0%	17.0%	3.1	1.3
All employees receive fair treatment whether male or female	9.0%	19.0%	19.0%	21.0%	32.0%	3.5	1.4
All employees are treated equally when it comes to promotions whether male or female.	11.0%	18.0%	18.0%	28.0%	25.0%	3.4	1.3
There are strong equity policies in the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology.	4.0%	5.9%	22.8%	32.7%	34.7%	3.9	1.1
The Ministry strictly adheres to sexual harassment policies in the organization	2.0%	3.0%	17.8%	27.7%	49.5%	4.2	1.0
Average						3.6	1.2

Source: Researcher Data (2023)

The results of the analysis showed that a response rate of 56%, with an average of 3.4 and a standard deviation of 1.2 agreed that the male to female ratio at the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology meets the constitutional affirmative rule. 41% of the respondents agreed that there are more female than male employees at the senior managerial level in the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology thus making a mean of 3.1 and a standard deviation of 1.3. Further, 53% of respondents, at a mean of 3.5 and standard deviation of 1.4 noted that all employees receive fair treatment irrespective of their gender. 53% response rate, making up 3.4 mean and 1.3 standard deviation agreed that all employees are treated fairly when it comes to promotions whether male or female. Also, 67.4% of employees, forming a mean of 3.9 and standard deviation of 1.1 agreed that there

are strong equity policies in the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology. 77.2% of respondents, with an average of 4.2 and a standard deviation of 1.0 stated that the Ministry strictly adheres to sexual harassment policies. The aggregate mean of 3.6 and standard deviation of 1.2 shows that most of the respondents agreed with the gender diversity statements. Key indicators of gender diversity as identified includes male to female ratio, fair treatment, and equity policies.

A. Correlation Analysis of Results

The correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between the variables in terms of strength and direction. Table 5 shows the outcome.

Table 5: Pearson Correlation

	Y	X ₁
Y Pearson Correlation	1	
Sig (2-tailed)		
X ₁ Pearson Correlation	.785**	1.000
Sig (2-tailed)	.000	.000
N	101	101

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Researcher Data (2023)

The results indicated that gender diversity had a strong positive association with employee performance ($r = .785^{**}$, $P = .000$) at 5% level of significance. This means that an attempt to increase gender diversity in an organization is closely associated to an increase in employee performance.

The findings resonated with Chepkemoi, Rop and Chepkwony (2022) who emphasized that tapping into the strength of both male and female employees can give an organization a competitive advantage as it creates room for interaction which improves performance outcomes.

B. Multiple Regression Analysis Results

Tables 6, 7 and 8 present the model summary, ANOVA, and regression of coefficient results respectively

Table 6: Regression Analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.885 ^a	0.783	0.767	0.01557
a. Predictors: (Constant), gender diversity				

R Square value is 0.783. This means that 78% of employee performance can be linked to the study variable. The remaining 22% of employee performance can be

explained by other diversity factors other factors that were not used in the scope of this research study.

Table 7: ANOVA

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.373	4	2.343	12.471	.000 ^b
	Residual	18.037	96	.188		
	Total	27.410	100			
a. Dependent Variable Y: Employee Performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), X ₁						

The ANOVA regression model in Table 4.10 indicate F statistic of 12.471 and reported P value of 0.000. Since the P value was less than the alpha value (P < .05), the proposed model is considered statistically significant (good fit) in

predicting the dependent variable. This implies that the independent variables (workforce diversity) are significant predictors of employee performance.

Table 8: Regression of Coefficient

Coefficients ^a							
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.574	.393			4.007	.000
	Gender Diversity	.163	.062	.100		1.014	.313
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance							

All the independent variables have identical (Likert) scales, however, the constant value in the model is insignificant, thus the use of standardized coefficients beta scores rather than unstandardized B-coefficients. The regression of coefficient results in Table 8 reveals that gender diversity had a positive and significant effect on employee performance ($\beta_1 = 0.163$, $P = .393$). This means that an increase in gender diversity by one unit would result in enhanced employee performance by 0.163 units. This implies that staff recognition contributes significantly to employee performance. The findings supported Chepkmoi, Rop and Chepkwony (2022) who stated that gender diversity has a significant influence on overall employee performance.

The estimated equation was as shown below:

$$\text{Employee performance} = 1.574 + 0.163 \text{ gender diversity} + \epsilon$$

Where ϵ is the estimation error

C. Gender Diversity and Employee Performance

In the objective, the researcher endeavored to examine the effect of gender diversity on employee performance at the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology. Most respondents agreed that male to female ratio, fair treatment at workplace, and equity policies are important indicators to measure gender diversity in an organization as seen from the descriptive results. The correlation analysis indicated that gender diversity has a positive and substantial effect on employee performance. Results from the regression analysis also showed that gender diversity at the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology impacted employee performance in a positive and significant manner. These findings agreed with Chepkmoi, Rop and Chepkwony (2022) who stated that gender diversity has a significant influence on overall employee performance. In addition, Mousa (2021) also concluded that gender diversity, if blended well with other diverse aspects, has a positive influence on employee performance.

The main objective of this research study was to determine the effect of workforce diversity on employee performance at the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology. Findings from the regression analysis indicated that workforce diversity explained up to 74% of changes in

employee performance in the organization, and this negates the hypothesis that workforce diversity does not affect employee performance.

VII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion of the Research Study

Following the findings related to the first objective, the researcher concluded that gender diversity has a positive significant effect on employee performance. Gender diversity thus plays an imperative role in employee performance. The study found out that male to female ratios, fair treatment, and existence of equity policies were vital aspects that promote gender diversity. Finally, the study concluded that workforce diversity had a positive significant effect on employee performance.

B. Recommendation of the Research Study

The study deduced that gender diversity positively and significantly contributes to employee performance. It urged organizations in the public sector to endeavor to have more gender diverse workforces through strategies like balanced male to female ratio, fair treatment, and equity policies. Instituting and strongly implementing anti-sexual harassment policies and upholding the view that all employees are evaluated on merit and not gender, the organization will realize an environment where all feel valued hence able to give their best for the success of the organization. Gender diversity strategies should not only be used as a means of achieving affirmative action requirements of the constitution but also to tap into the competitive advantage that arises when both male and female employees achieve maximum potential.

C. Implication of the Research Study on Human Resource Practice

The research study findings indicate that employee diversity plays a pivotal role in enhancing employee performance in organizations of all specializations and sizes. Therefore, organizations operating in the public sector such as ministries, parastatals and commissions should ensure they always have a diverse workforce. Organizations should major in improving workforce diversity in terms of gender not only for compliance but also to improve employee performance. Through the presentation of empirical evidence on the role workforce diversity plays on employee performance, the research study makes a notable contribution to the field of human resource management and practice through adding literature and statistics.

The Human Resource department at the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology will also identify and maximize workforce diversity aspects highlighted in this study to impact on employee performance. Moreover, organizations in the public sector, more so the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology will realize that employees work best when in a diverse environment thus formulate or improve policies that will ensure equity and non-discrimination to enhance diversity which in the long run ensures employees are able to maximize potential and achieve synergy for continuously improved performance.

D. Recommendation for Further Research

This research study paid attention to the effect of workforce diversity on employee performance at the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology. Research findings showed that the independent variables of workforce diversity-gender- contribute to 78% change in employee performance which is the dependent variable. Further research is recommended on other aspects of workforce diversity in the public sector to account for the remaining 22% to make employee performance 100%. In addition, this research study only focused on the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology which is a representation of the public sector workforce. However, diversity cuts across both public and private organizations. Therefore, similar research can be carried out in the private sector for purposes of comparison.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Alromaihi, M. A., Alshomaly, Z. A., & George, S. (2017). Job satisfaction and employee performance: A theoretical review of the relationship between the two variables. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 1-20.
- [2]. Anyango, O. M., & Florah, O. M. (2019). Workforce Diversity and Performance of Kisumu Law Courts, Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 10(12).
- [3]. Armstrong, M. (2021). *Performance management*. Kogan Page limited.
- [4]. Armstrong, M., & Taylor, S. (2023). *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice: A Guide to the Theory and Practice of People Management*. Kogan Page Publishers.
- [5]. Barang'a, H. K., & Maende, C. (2019). Workforce Diversity on Employee Performance in the Office of the Attorney General and Department of Justice, Kenya. *International Journal of Current Aspects*, 3(V), 252-266.
- [6]. Chepkemoi, G., Rop, W., & Chepkwony, P. (2022). The Relationship between Gender Diversity and Employee Performance in the County Government of Bomet, Kenya. *East African Journal of Business and Economics*, 5(1), 90-98.
- [7]. Cherry, K. (2018). Attitudes and behavior in psychology. *Verywell mind*.
- [8]. Kenya Institute for Public Policy Research & Analysis (2020): Kenya Economic Report 2020. Accessed on 13/03/2023
https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwjQ28XKj4_3AhUQwKQKHcltAnQQFnoEACQAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fkippra.or.ke%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2021%2F02%2FKenya-Economic-Report-2020.pdf&usg=AOvVaw0p78Y6z2qUtUNNs8MnA6Z
- [9]. Khan, F., Sohail, A., Sufyan, M., Uddin, M., & Basit, A. (2019). The effect of workforce diversity on employee performance in Higher Education Sector. *Journal of Management Info*, 6(3), 1-8.

- [10]. Krishnan, D. S. G. (2020). Gender diversity in the workplace and its effects on employees' performance. *Journal of the Social Sciences*.
- [11]. Kundu, S. C., & Mor, A. (2017). Workforce diversity and organizational performance: a study of IT industry in India. *Employee Relations*.
- [12]. Mekasha, S. (2020). *Effect of Workforce Diversity on Employee Performance: The Case of Save the Children Ethiopia* (doctoral dissertation, St. Mary's university).
- [13]. Mithaug, D. E. (1996). *Equal opportunity theory*. Sage.
- [14]. Mousa, M. (2021). Does gender diversity affect workplace happiness for academics? The role of diversity management and organizational inclusion. *Public Organization Review*, 21(1), 119-135.
- [15]. Mugenda, O., & Mugenda, A. (2019). *Research Methods; Qualitative and Quantitative and mixed methods approaches*.
- [16]. Odhiambo, M. W., Gachoka, H. G., & Rambo, C. M. (2018). Relationship between age diversity and employee performance of public universities in Western Kenya. <http://41.204.161.209/handle/11295/107225>
- [17]. Ogola, M. (2017). The influence of individualized consideration leadership behavior on employee performance in small and medium enterprises in Kenya. <http://41.204.183.105/handle/11732/4227>
- [18]. Pandey, P., & Pandey, M. M. (2021). *Research methodology tools and techniques*. Bridge Center
- [19]. Sama, M.C, Ramsy, A.A, & Fonchamnyo, D.C. (2020). *Research Methodology and Scientific Writing; Theory and Practice*. Design House.
- [20]. Setati, S. T., Zhuwao, S., Ngirande, H., & Ndlovu, W. (2019). Gender diversity, ethnic diversity and employee performance in a South African higher education institution. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17(1), 1-8.
- [21]. The Parliament of Kenya: Members of the National Assembly. Accessed on 15.02.2023 <http://www.parliament.go.ke/the-national-assembly/mps>
- [22]. U.S Bureau of Labor Statistics: Demographics. Accessed on 16.02.2023 <https://www.bls.gov/cps/demographics.htm#race>